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<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-02575-0>

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How deep is your trust? A comparative user requirements' analysis of automation in medical and mobility technologies

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In a changing world full of innovative technologies, trust and trust requirements are increasingly important for designing user-centred systems and ensuring their long-term implementation. In this study, we explored and compared the requirements of future users to build trust in the two contexts of medical and mobility technology by considering Ambient Assisted Living technologies (AAL) and Shared Autonomous Vehicles (SAV). We conducted an online survey study with $N = 143$ participants. The results show significant differences in the evaluation of individual trust requirements in the two contexts about data sharing, data privacy and security as well as customization. Using a cluster analysis, we identified distinct user groups and trust personalities in both contexts (medicine and mobility). The clusters differ in terms of innovation openness and risk readiness, initial trust, and presence of chronic illness. Correlation analyses revealed significant relationships between people's initial perceived trust in technology in the two contexts and their assessment of trust requirements, as well as their behavioural intentions to use SAV or AAL systems. Our findings indicate that trust requirements are context-specific and influenced by individual characteristics. This knowledge can be used to inform developers and distributors of technologies to design, build, and manage systems that meet the needs of future users.

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Introduction and background

Nowadays, there is an increasing support of assistive and autonomous technologies in different contexts like in the health sector, mobility, and energy supply (Climent-Pérez et al. 2020; Hansen and Sener, 2023; Zhang et al. 2010). Processes that are automated, enhanced, or assisted by technological interventions can be a relief for the users and at the same time users have to rely on new technologies in their daily lives. What is greeted with joy and technical curiosity for some users (Kim and Chiu, 2018) may be a problem for others, as, for example, a perceived dependence on technology or loss of control can lead to uncertainty and limit the willingness to use (Jaschinski and Allouch, 2015; Schmidt et al. 2015). In the following, the relevance of the social science perspective on the perception and acceptance of innovative technologies and the role of perceived trust will be presented. First, findings from the current state of research will be described at an overarching level. This is followed by an argument as to why it is necessary to consider acceptance and trust in a contextual comparison. To further justify the choice of the medical and mobility contexts in this study, global challenges and changes in society are outlined. This is followed by a more detailed description of the state of research in the existing contexts to summarise previous findings and define relevant research gaps.

Relevance of the social science approach to acceptance and trust and related work

Human interaction is especially important in assistive and autonomous technologies. Many of these technologies have an interface through which humans, often laypeople interact with the technology (see, e.g., Blackman et al. 2016) for a review of AAL technology and Janssen et al. (2019) for a cross-contextual review of human-automation interaction, including driving automation). Because of this interplay, not only the technical features, but also the human perceptions of these features are important for the correct and continuous use of technologies, especially since incorrect handling of technologies can have dramatic consequences: for example, when users wrongly rely on the functioning of a technology or, conversely, when they intervene when this would not be necessary, which is defined by Parasuraman and Riley (1997) as the *disuse* (i.e., underreliance) and *misuse* (i.e., overreliance) of automation. This is particularly relevant in safety-critical contexts such as automated driving (De Winter et al. 2022) and medicine (Grissinger, 2019), which is why we need to understand users' perceptions of novel technologies.

The way a technology is perceived (e.g., as trustworthy or risky) can influence the willingness to use or reject it (Pavlou, 2003). To predict the successful adoption of a technology, acceptance modelling is often used to relate the perceived benefits and barriers of a technology to different application contexts, cultures, and user diversity (AlQudah et al. 2021; Choukou et al. 2021; Offermann-van Heek and Ziefle, 2019). The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) focuses on the perceived usefulness and ease of use of a system to predict the usage intention (Davis, 1989). Later models add technical, social, and human factors (e.g., performance expectations, social influence, experience, demographics), as well as the perceived value of a technology (e.g., price/utility trade-offs) (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000; Venkatesh and Bala, 2008; Venkatesh et al. 2003, 2012; Kim et al. 2007). Human trust is also included in the assessment of acceptance (Otten et al. 2023; Shuhaiber et al. 2023; Vervier et al. 2019), i.e., the perceived trustworthiness of a technology based on factors such as disposition, knowledge, and cost-benefit calculations (Weck and Afanassieva, 2023). Trust shows direct correlations with the intention to use a system, but also mediating effects, e.g.,

of public, production, and data policies in building trust and managing distrust in technology use (Bodó, 2021; Ghazizadeh et al. 2012). As the impact of trust on acceptance seems to be determined by directly and indirectly observable factors, knowledge about their interplay is equally complex and of great relevance for scientific research and technology development.

Trust and trust transfer are difficult concepts to define without universal conclusions across disciplines (McKnight and Chervany, 2001; McKnight et al. 2011). Therefore, descriptions of trust vary depending on the perspective (e.g., organisational, personal, technological) (Söderström, 2009). Mayer et al. (1995) provided an influential model of organisational trust, identifying predictors (e.g., perceived trustworthiness) and outcomes (e.g., likelihood of *risk-taking* in a relationship) of it by examining existing literature. Since then, other researchers applied these conceptualisations in contexts relating to automation, outlining influences of risk and credibility in websites (Corritore et al. 2003), trust and acceptance in online shopping (Gefen et al. 2003), and trust and antitrust in cyber-domains (Hoffman et al. 2009). Hoff and Bashir (2015) conceptualised trust in automation based on an extensive literature review and found three distinct layers of trust prior to and during interaction: dispositional, situational, and learned. Dispositional trust is defined as "an individual's overall tendency to trust automation" (p. 413) and is influenced by demographics, culture, and personality; situational trust is determined by factors of a usage situation, e.g., the type of system and the user's confidence; learned trust is built initially through expectations and dynamically during interaction through perceived usefulness, for example. Bodó (2021) has additionally argued that technologies mediate interpersonal relationships of trust with the service they carry. This indicates that not only technological features, but also interpersonal trust perceptions could be relevant in the understanding of trust in automation. It is therefore important to investigate how trust and acceptance manifest in different technologies.

Importance of considering acceptance and trust in contextual comparison

Technology is important in many areas of life. Although the use of technology can be very specific, different contexts of use often face similar challenges when introducing new technologies, for example when it comes to issues such as privacy and security, whether it is the use of medical devices integrated into people's living environment or the use of autonomous vehicles in mobility. It is therefore useful to study acceptance and trust building in different contexts to gain a broader understanding of public perceptions of technology and its societal impacts. From a scientific perspective, comparative studies are relevant to explore relationships and evaluation patterns as a basis for the ongoing development of models and theories that contribute to the understanding of acceptance and trust. The results can be used to share new approaches to innovation management across sectors, to help shaping policy decisions and regulations in a way that takes user needs into account, and to make the development and adoption of technology in different areas of life more meaningful. The choice of medical and mobility contexts in the present study is related to current societal changes and global challenges that particularly affect both contexts, as outlined below. We then show how the use of technological innovation can help to address the challenges described in each context.

Social changes and their impact on the health and mobility sectors

In Germany, as in other parts of the world, we are experiencing demographic change, i.e., the society is ageing. In the coming

years, the proportion of people of working age (20–66) will decrease, while the proportion of people aged 67 and over will increase (Federal Statistical Office, 2023). As the likelihood of chronic diseases and multimorbidity grows with age (RKL, 2023), many people will need assistance with activities of daily living. Specifically in the context of medicine, ageing and care dependence are an important topics. In conjunction with an increasing healthcare worker shortage, enabling older adults to live independently in their own home is becoming increasingly more salient (Peek et al. 2014; WHO, 2002). The aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic has further exacerbated this evolution. Research shows that the frequency to consult medical services has decreased bringing about problems, such as maintaining the relationship with physicians in people with chronic diseases. However, care needs are equally as high and with the next generation, the so-called baby boomers, heading for retirement, solutions for achieving both independence and security of care are needed (Menning and Hoffmann, 2009; Börsch-Supan et al. 2015). The demographic change also has implications for the mobility sector in that it will strengthen the need for inclusive mobility services that enable all people, regardless of their health condition, to move independently and safely for as long as their individual circumstances allow.

Technological solutions for health and mobility

As a way of mitigating social changes and resulting challenges, technological solutions are continuously being developed and advanced. In the realm of medical technologies, AAL technologies are a promising solution (Blackman et al. 2016; Climent-Pérez et al. 2020). They encompass a wide range of applications including wearables and ambient installed sensors that track health information such as vital parameters, step counts, activities of daily living, etc. (Climent-Pérez et al. 2020). Collectively, AAL technologies and systems aim to enable older adults and/or people in need of care to live independently at home or in care residences while still having the security of help, for instance in the case of a fall (Blackman et al. 2016). More specifically, video-based AAL technologies using ambient sensors installed in a person's home provide an immense amount of information with a single sensor, i.e., a type of camera. These can be readily interpreted as video-recordings are intuitive to the user, while each camera provides varying levels of detail, depending on the needs of the user (Hashemifard et al. 2023; Mucha and Kampel, 2022; Rashidi and Miahilidis, 2013). Notifications of changes in the health status or an emergency (such as a fall or prolonged inactivity) of the person can be sent to previously approved persons, such as care personnel or relatives, respecting the data and privacy of the user. Overall, (video-based) AAL technologies capture a lot of information with relatively little need for interaction (Cardinaux et al. 2011; Ravi et al. 2021).

In the mobility sector, technological progress is advancing in the development of alternative drive technologies, such as battery electric vehicles, and automated driving. The well-known SAE J3016 standard describes and classifies motor vehicle driving automation systems into six levels ranging from no driving automation (Level 0) to full driving automation (Level 5) (SAE International, 2021). Level 5 describes the ability of the vehicle to drive autonomously under all road conditions, i.e., without the intervention or involvement of a person at the wheel, who is thus no longer needed: drivers become passengers. Electrified autonomous driving with shared vehicles and pooled rides is a much-discussed way to make road transportation more sustainable, efficient, and safe (Greenblatt and Shaheen, 2015; Kovačić et al. 2022; Santos, 2018). New business models are emerging that understand mobility as a service and offer customized solutions

tailored to the user's needs (Storme et al. 2021). In addition to shared mobility and ride-pooling, this includes the development of on-demand mobility services which, unlike traditional public transportation, operate without timetables and stops, similar to taxis (Hansen and Sener, 2023; Machado et al. 2018). Our research scenario combines these transportation trends by describing an autonomous shuttle service using electric vehicles to transport small groups on demand. For an overview of autonomous shuttles in real-world operation, see Iclodean et al. (2020).

Users perspective on automation, acceptance, and trust in health and mobility. Because trust has behavioural implications in terms of acceptance (Lee and See, 2004), trust perceptions and attitudes are increasingly used to model technology adoption in various application domains, such as mobile banking (Merhi et al. 2019), food delivery app usage (Su et al. 2022), online shopping (Denaputri and Usman, 2020), AI-based mobile health chatbot services (Patil and Kulkarni, 2022), and driverless automated shuttles (Nordhoff et al. 2021). While there are detailed findings on the perception and evaluation of trust regarding individual, sometimes very specific technologies (Steinke et al. 2014; for an overview, see McKnight et al. 2011), the state of research on context-comparative trust formation is incomplete. Initial empirical studies compare factors related to trust and acceptance in the areas of mobility and smart homes (Brell et al. 2019), and care and manufacturing (Biermann et al. 2020). In addition, literature-based critical reflections have been made on the trustworthiness of robots and automated systems in different application domains (including public, private, and professional) and with respect to different types of artificial intelligence (AI). Regarding video-based AAL and SAV, it has been shown that people's understanding of what constitutes and conditions (dis) trust (e.g., cognition and affection) varies depending on the context (Biermann et al. 2023a). However, an analysis of the underlying prerequisites for trust formation in contextual comparison is missing so far. Therefore, the current state of research on acceptance and trust is described for each context below.

Users perspective on AAL technology. There are multiple studies that point towards a dynamic view on the acceptance of AAL technologies, meaning that it is dependent on many technological, individual, and contextual factors. There are both benefits as well as barriers to the adoption of such technologies and systems (Jaschinski and Allouch, 2015; Wilkowska et al. 2021). Some of these benefits include a sense of security regarding medical care, relief of care burden on oneself and others, added value to their daily life, and medical necessity (Jaschinski et al. 2021; Offermann-van Heek et al. 2019). There are many benefits, most of which are highly individual, that – if satisfied – increase the likelihood of a person accepting and thus intending to use a given system. However, these are constantly traded off against the barriers, which often include usability issues, perceived privacy invasion, data access, and trust issues. When the barriers outweigh the benefits, the probability of acceptance is lowered significantly (Rashidi and Miahilidis, 2013; Jaschinski et al. 2021; Offermann-van Heek et al. 2019; Otten et al. 2023). Therefore, personalisation of AAL technologies that protect both the privacy of the users while maintaining their right to control who has access to their data, is crucial in mediating the evaluation of benefits and barriers (Maidhof et al. 2023). Not only are these perceived factors relevant, other user-specific influences are also highly predictive of the behavioural intention to use a given AAL system, i.e., a facet of the overall acceptance evaluation. This includes the general affinity for technology, openness for change

or innovation, and trust in AAL systems (Barr, 2023; Halbach et al. 2018). The role of trust in the overall acceptance of AAL technology has been investigated in multiple studies where higher levels of trust were associated with higher levels of acceptance (Steinke et al. 2012, 2014; Otten et al. 2023; Otten and Ziefle, 2022; Vervier et al. 2018, 2019; Wilkowska et al. 2021). However, in order to understand how trust is built, requirements of it must be investigated. Previous studies have tried to capture trust requirements, but how these relate to overall perceptions of trust has not been studied (Otten et al. 2023; Otten and Ziefle, 2022). Seeing as requirements for trust are modifiable to a certain extent, understanding which are considered important for the development of trust in AAL technologies is imperative to change trust for the better. In turn, the predictive role of trust can then be translated to how this shapes the behavioural intention to use AAL technologies and systems. In addition, it is unclear whether trust and trust requirements can be considered universal in the acceptance of technologies, whether there are context-specific influences in the AAL sector or whether the same requirements might have different significance. Comparing technology contexts could help in providing practical guidelines that are adjusted to each technological sector.

Users' perspective on Shared Autonomous Vehicles (SAV). Within the mobility context and SAV, there are two main challenges for acceptance: first, the shift from individual motorized transportation to collective transportation with possibly unfamiliar passengers, and second, the transfer of driving tasks and responsibilities to an autonomous system. The perceived need to own a car has been identified as a major barrier to the adoption of new mobility services, especially among people with car-centric attitudes and behaviours and below-average environmental friendliness (Alonso-González et al. 2020). Mobility services in which individuals not only share a vehicle but also travel together (i.e., pooled rides) are perceived as less attractive than private cars, for example, in terms of waiting and travel time and travel comfort (Santos, 2018). Sharing anxiety describes users' fear of unpredictable behaviour of fellow passengers and limits their willingness to share rides, especially in SAV (Dolins et al. 2021). This may be due to a lack of responsive personnel on board. The incentives and barriers to the use of SAV have been investigated in detail in several studies: for example, considering the purpose of a trip and fellow travellers, interface communication, human factors (e.g., perceived importance of car ownership, driving enjoyment) and user diversity (e.g., gender differences), using different methods of empirical social research (interviews, questionnaires, test runs) (Biermann et al. 2020; Clayton et al. 2020; Lundgren et al. 2020; Nordhoff et al. 2019; Philipsen et al. 2019; 2020). A central role in attitude and intention to use is the perceived security, need for control, and perceived trust (Nordhoff et al. 2021). It is reasonable to assume that perceived risks and uncertainties in this regard may limit acceptance. In a choice task between a SAV and a traditional mobility service with a human driver, shuttle voters showed higher initial trust in the new mobility service, but also higher levels of trust in other areas (interpersonal, technological); the others, while not distrustful of technology in general, were sceptical of the mobility innovation (Biermann et al. 2023b). Hence, an essential part of acceptance research is to find out what different user groups require from SAV to trust them, and which features of the service and the environment as well as the technology are perceived as particularly relevant and crucial for trust. So far, it is evident that the conditions for building trust in SAV depend on the user's perspective (Biermann et al. 2022): The key conditions for trusting an SAV are different in detail for people with a trusting attitude towards an SAV than for sceptics. Both groups differed

significantly in socio-demographic and attitudinal data. While the safety of the vehicle and the manufacturer's liability in case of damage seemed to be relevant for all, the possibility to control the vehicle was particularly important for the sceptics. However, it needs to be further explored to what extent these are specific to the mobility sector, and how they relate to trust and may vary in other application fields. Cross-contextual findings would have implications for the design and development of technological innovations for the specific use case and for innovation management in general and are therefore of great scientific and practical interest.

Research gap and objectives of this study

There is a lot of evidence about acceptance and trust-building in different contexts. Different studies have looked at different factors, including perceived benefits and barriers and human factors, such as dispositions. The results show that there is an overlap of trust-relevant factors across contexts, for example with regard to privacy-related aspects. What is lacking is a bundled consideration of these aspects in a joint study, also to identify correlations with willingness to use. This study aims to fill this research gap. The aspects of trust and acceptance identified as relevant in the current state of research and based on qualitative preliminary studies (see Section "Methods and Materials") were formulated as generically as possible in this study in order to enable comparison and because the initial interest in knowledge was to explore and measure contextual differences and similarities at a higher level. The results of this study can then be used in follow-up studies to zoom in on and specify individual aspects that are found to be relevant for both contexts.

As a research object, we have focused on the requirements for building trust in a contextual comparison. In a scenario-based approach, we investigated the trust perceptions of future users of assistive and autonomous technologies in the medical and mobility domains. We defined two research scenarios (see Appendix A for full scenario descriptions):

1. In the medical domain, the focus was on the use of video-based Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) technologies that promote the independence of people in need of care, ensure their safety, and reduce the workload of caregivers.
2. In the area of mobility, the use of a new driving service with shared autonomous vehicles (SAV) was described to address the major challenges of today's transport sector (environmental protection, transport efficiency and safety, etc.) and at the same time provide social opportunities, e.g., the mobilization of people who are unable to drive themselves due to age, health, or other reasons (e.g., no driving license).

We have chosen these contexts because of their relevance to society and to each individual (see Section "Importance of Considering Acceptance and Trust in Contextual Comparison"). In other words, everyone has personal contact with health and mobility issues and is likely to be directly or indirectly affected by potential changes. Therefore, not only was everyone eligible to participate in our study, but the results are also socially relevant. This study aims to investigate and compare initially perceived trust requirements (i.e., scenario-based, prior to actual interaction) in the two contexts of medical and mobility technologies. Following established trust frameworks (e.g., Hoff and Bashir, 2015), we analysed similarities and differences in trust ratings and how they relate to contextual and human factors. However, because of the relative lack of comparison in the literature, no specific hypotheses and predictions will be tied to the research questions and the study follows an exploratory approach. The following research questions (RQ) will be answered:

1. How are trust requirements in AAL technology and SAV evaluated from the user's perspective?
2. Can individuals be grouped on the basis of their response to the trust-building requirements set for assessment in their respective contexts of use, in order to define possible target groups?
3. How are trust perceptions and trust requirements in the two contexts related to the behavioural intention to use a given system?

Methods and Materials

To answer our research questions, we conducted a survey with two scenarios pertaining to the mobility and medical context. Prior to this questionnaire study, semi-structured interviews were conducted with nine participants (four women and five men, age range 25–76 years) to explore the trust requirements in the two contexts of AAL and SAV and people's perceptions of trust in these contexts. The respondents were asked, among other things, in which situations and under which circumstances they would rely on automation in the areas of mobility and medicine, and what they consider to be the prerequisites for building trust in AAL or SAV. The results were used to develop statements that could be measured as items on Likert scales, adding to the current state of research. In the following, the research design and examined variables are presented. We used self-developed items based on qualitative interviews and preliminary studies (Biermann et al. 2023b; Otten et al. 2023) and validated scales to assess answers. Cronbach's alpha (α) was used to assess the reliability of all scales used in the questionnaire. Overall reliability was sufficient (≥ 0.7). See Appendix B for a complete list of items and construct assignments, with references and scale reliability information.

Measures

Innovation readiness. This construct was based on Urban and Pfenning (1999) and measured in seven items on a 6-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("disagree completely") to 6 ("agree completely"). It has shown good reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.81$). Example items include "Technical developments guarantee social progress" and "I enjoy experiencing technical progress".

Dispositional trust. This construct was based on Beierlein et al. (2014; e.g., "In general, people can be trusted"), self-developed items from the interviews and previous research (Biermann et al. 2023b; e.g., "I usually trust that the other person will not lie to me"). It was measured in eight items on a 6-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("disagree completely") to 6 ("agree completely") and has shown good reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.84$).

Risk perception. Risk perception was measured in a single item ("How risk-taking would you describe yourself to be?") on a 6-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("not at all risk-taking") to 6 ("totally risk-taking") (Beierlein et al. 2015).

Trust requirements. The evaluations of trust requirements (i.e., the level of agreement that any item would be considered a condition of trust development) were based on the interviews and previous research (Otten et al. 2023) and measured in ten items on a 6-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("disagree completely") to 6 ("agree completely"). In each scenario, they were adapted to matching the specific technology, i.e., SAV or AAL. Reliability was good for both contexts (AAL: Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.89$; SAV: Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.9$). Example items include "I would only trust the SAV/AAL system if I can decide who my share my data" and

"I would only trust the SAV/AAL system if it has a low error rate".

Behavioural intention to use. This construct was measured in a single item on a 6-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("not at all risk-taking") to 6 ("totally risk-taking") based on Davis (1989) and adapted to each context.

Initial trust. The initial trust of the system was based on Jian et al. (2000; e.g., "Decisions that SAV/AAL systems make, would have negative consequences"), based on the interviews and inspired by Biermann et al. (2023b; e.g., "Whether I trust the SAV/AAL system plays an important role in my decision to use it"). It was measured in four items on a 6-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("not at all risk-taking") to 6 ("totally risk-taking") in both contexts respectively. Reliability was adequate for both contexts (AAL: Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.65$; SAV: Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.71$).

Research design and procedure. The survey was conducted in Germany between summer and autumn 2022. The survey link was distributed through various channels, including social media (e.g., Facebook) and topic-specific online platforms and forums as well as distributions in the research team's social network via direct addresses, e.g., by mail. The study has been carried out in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki's ethical guidelines. Participants were informed that their data would be analysed anonymously for scientific purposes only and would not be passed on to third parties (in compliance with scientific data protection guidelines). They were also informed that there were no wrong or right answers. They were encouraged to answer the questions as intuitively as possible. This was to avoid effects of social desirability in the response behaviour. Participation in the survey was voluntary without monetary compensation or other incentives. Informed consent was obtained prior to participation.

The survey consisted of two parts; an overview can be found in Fig. 1. In the first part, participants had to provide demographic information on age, gender, educational level, and health status, i.e., "Any chronic physical and/or mental health conditions?" (yes/no). In addition, we asked about their personality, i.e., innovation readiness, dispositional trust and the participants' risk perception.

The second part consisted of two scenarios which were presented to the participants in a randomised order: In the description on medical technology, participants were asked to imagine a video-based AAL system in their home with the purpose of analysing abnormal movements to prevent falls and alarming selected contact in case of a fall. This was phrased more generally as the application for the AAL technologies can differ based on the individual needs of the user. Particularly for AAL systems, the use case can differ substantially and has to be customisable for the user. In the mobility technology scenario, participants were asked to imagine a shuttle service with SAV that is offered as a complement to conventional public transportation, is bookable on-demand (i.e., has no schedules or stops), and can be customized (e.g., in terms of equipment). After each scenario, participants were asked about specific trust requirements. Next, the behavioural intention to use the given system and the initial trust in the system was asked for.

Statistical analyses. Concerning our first research question on how the participants evaluate trust requirements in each context (RQ1), we initially used descriptive statistics, i.e., means (M) and standard deviations (SD). We then computed dependent samples t-tests on each item pair to investigate significant differences. Next, we conducted cluster analyses based on the subjects'

Fig. 1 Overview of the Research Design.

assessment of trust requirements in each context, beginning with a two-step cluster and following up with a k-means cluster using the recommended cluster groups as a restriction (RQ2). To investigate group differences of the identified cluster in each context, we conducted independent samples t-tests, ANOVA's, and chi-square tests based on the conceptualisation of the predictor variables, i.e., categorical or continuous, two or more groups to compare. Lastly, we conducted correlation analyses to explore relationships between trust (perceptions and requirements) and behavioural intention to use either SAV or AAL systems (RQ3).

The significance level (α) was set at 5%. Cohen's d was reported to indicate effect size.

Sample. After data cleaning, i.e., removing speeders (>3 SD's below the mean duration) and unfinished surveys ($>50\%$ of missing data), $N=143$ participants were considered for the analyses. There were slightly more females ($N=78$; 54.5%) than males ($N=64$; 44.8%) and one participant that identified as diverse (0.7%). The sample was relatively young overall with a mean of 37.41 years ($SD=13.64$; Range: 19–81) and highly educated with nearly 50% of the participants holding a post-graduate degree ($N=71$). Another 36.1% ($N=52$) possessed full and/or partial university entrance qualifications. The mean score on innovation readiness was 3.94 ($SD=1.3$), while the mean score on dispositional trust was 3.81 ($SD=0.7$) and the mean score for innovation readiness was 3.95 ($SD=0.54$). Mean scores on initial trust were 4.55 ($SD=0.61$) in the medical context and 4.65 ($SD=0.62$) in the mobility context.

Results

In this chapter, the results of the statistical analyses are presented in the order of the research questions outlined above. Before presenting the findings to answer the research questions posed, a description of the baseline findings on initial perceived trust and willingness to use AAL and SAV technologies is provided. The

findings provide valuable insights into perceptions and evaluations, and reveal underlying narratives that can be used to frame subsequent findings.

Trust and usage intention in contextual comparison: general findings. Potential differences between the two contexts with respect to the variables *initial trust* and *behavioural intention* were investigated using dependent samples t-tests. Initial trust was higher in the mobility context than in the medical context ("Decisions that the system makes, would have negative consequences" SAV: $M=3.06$, $SD=0.85$, AAL: $M=2.93$, $SD=0.8$; "I would only use this system if I felt like I could trust it" SAV: $M=4.87$, $SD=0.94$, AAL: $M=4.66$, $SD=0.92$; "Whether or not I trust the system plays a role in my decision to use it" SAV: $M=4.84$, $SD=0.99$, AAL: $M=4.62$, $SD=0.99$; "If I did not trust the system, I would not use it" SAV: $M=4.94$, $SD=0.91$, AAL: $M=4.85$, $SD=0.88$). Only the items "I would only use this system if I felt like I could trust it" ($t(142)=-2.68$, $p=0.008$, $d=0.22$) and "Whether or not I trust the system plays a role in my decision to use it" ($t(142)=-2.71$, $p=0.008$, $d=0.23$) were significantly different in the two contexts. The behavioural intention to use a given system was slightly higher in the medical context ($M=4.03$, $SD=1$) than in the mobility context ($M=3.99$, $SD=0.13$). However, this difference was not significant ($t(142)=0.54$, $p=0.59$).

Trust requirements in contextual comparison (RQ1). Figure 2 shows the assessed trust requirements within the given contexts. Overall, aspects regarding the reliability of technologies were the most accepted in both contexts: "if it has a low error rate" (SAV: $M=5.25$, $SD=0.91$; AAL: $M=5.14$, $SD=0.92$) and "if it is thoroughly researched" (SAV: $M=5.1$, $SD=1.01$; AAL: $M=5.04$, $SD=0.82$).

In the mobility context, requirements followed concerning the market maturity ("if it is ready for the market/has the TÜV-sign¹": $M=4.89$, $SD=1.14$), information status ("if I have informed myself well about it": $M=4.78$, $SD=1.07$), and aspects regarding data topics: "if I can decide who my see my data" ($M=4.76$, $SD=1.21$), "who may share my data" ($M=4.72$, $SD=1.25$), and "who may save my data" ($M=4.69$, $SD=1.25$). The three least accepted items in the mobility context were related to aspects of privacy ("if my privacy is of highest priority": $M=4.58$, $SD=1.28$) and security ("if data security is of highest priority": $M=4.53$, $SD=1.27$), as well as customization ("if the offer is individually tailored to me": $M=4.09$, $SD=1.18$) – although agreement with these requirements was still high.

In the medical context, the response behaviour looked somewhat different. Here, data privacy issues were most important, followed by market maturity: "who may share my data" ($M=5.04$, $SD=0.92$), "who may see my data" ($M=5.03$, $SD=0.97$), "if it is ready for the market" ($M=4.99$, $SD=0.1.02$), and "who may save my data" ($M=4.97$, $SD=1.02$). The items "if I have informed myself well about it" ($M=4.87$, $SD=0.93$) and "if my privacy is of highest priority" ($M=4.87$, $SD=1.13$) were equally accepted. As in the mobility context, the two least accepted conditions were related to security ("if data security is of highest priority": $M=4.83$, $SD=1.14$) and customization ("if it is individually tailored to me": $M=4.57$, $SD=0.97$).

Dependent samples t-tests were carried out to outline significant differences between the evaluation of trust requirements in the two contexts (see Fig. 2). As the dependent variable was changed with each test, no Bonferroni correction was applied. As already indicated in the evaluation of the descriptive statistics, significant differences were obtained regarding aspects of data security and privacy: "if data security is of highest priority"

Fig. 2 Mean evaluations of trust requirements in contextual comparison with standard deviations. Items begin with “I would only trust the system...” Note: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$.

($t(142) = -2.795$; $p = 0.006$, Cohen’s $d = 0.23$), “who may see my data” ($t(142) = -2.502$; $p = 0.013$, Cohen’s $d = 0.21$), “if my privacy is of highest priority” ($t(142) = -4.199$; $p < 0.001$, Cohen’s $d = 0.35$), “who may store my data” ($t(142) = -2.764$; $p = 0.006$, Cohen’s $d = 0.23$), “who may share my data” ($t(142) = -3.039$; $p = 0.003$, Cohen’s $d = 0.25$). Apart from data sharing, these questioned trust requirements were all more relevant to the AAL context (i.e., comparatively more agreement here). Besides, a significant difference was found with regard to customization, which was comparatively less important for trust building in both contexts (based on the level of agreement), especially in the mobility context: “if it is individually tailored to me” ($t(142) = -4.773$; $p < 0.001$, Cohen’s $d = 0.4$).

Identification of Trust Groups (RQ2). As a first step, the research showed differences in the perception and evaluation of the requirements for building trust depending on the context of use. Next, cluster analyses were carried out to determine the extent to which different people evaluate the requirements differently in the respective contexts to define possible target groups.

In the medical context, a two-step cluster analysis was conducted revealing two groups. Next, a k-means cluster analysis was conducted limiting the number of groups to two as indicated by the two-step analysis. According to these analyses, there were $N = 89$ in the first and $N = 54$ in the second cluster. The first group ($M = 5.39$, $SD = 0.36$) had an overall higher mean on the evaluation of trust requirements in AAL systems than the second group ($M = 4.21$, $SD = 0.51$). In other words, on average, Group 1 expressed strong agreement with the requirements for building trust in AAL systems, while Group 2 also expressed agreement, but comparatively less strongly. To investigate whether this difference was statistically significant, an independent samples t-test with the two groups as the independent variable and aggregated trust requirements in AAL as the dependent variable was conducted whereby a significant difference was found ($t(141) = 16.16$, $p < 0.001$, $d = 2.79$).

In the mobility context, a two-step cluster analysis was conducted revealing three groups. Next, a k-means cluster analysis was conducted limiting the number of groups to three as indicated by the two-step analysis. According to these analyses, there were $N = 58$ in the first, $N = 18$ in the second, and $N = 67$ in the third cluster. The first group ($M = 5.54$, $SD = 0.28$) had the highest mean score on the evaluation of trust requirements in SAV, followed by the third ($M = 4.47$, $SD = 0.34$) and second

($M = 3.19$, $SD = 0.52$) cluster. In other words, Group 1 on average strongly agreed with the requirements for building trust in SAV, Group 2 also agreed, but comparatively less strongly, and Group 3 on average tended to disagree with the requirements for building trust. To investigate whether this difference was statistically significant, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the three groups as the independent variable and aggregated trust requirements in SAV as the dependent variable was conducted whereby a significant effect was found ($F(2,140) = 353.6$, $p < 0.001$).

Trust groups differences across contexts. We investigated whether the identified clusters differed on user characteristics, i.e., age, education, gender, presence of chronic illness, dispositional trust, innovation readiness, risk readiness, and initial trust. The results are presented below and can be found in Tables 1 and 2.

Regarding the clusters identified in the medical context, five independent samples t-tests were conducted with the two trust groups as the independent variable and age, dispositional trust, innovation readiness, risk readiness, and initial trust perceptions as respective dependent variables. No significant differences were found for the variables age, and dispositional trust. We found significant differences between the two trust groups and their levels of risk ($t(141) = -2.55$, $p = 0.012$, $d = 0.44$) and innovation readiness ($t(141) = -2.85$, $p = 0.005$, $d = 0.49$). Upon inspection of the descriptive statistics, we found that Group 1, i.e., those who strongly agreed on average with the requirements for trust building, had a lower mean on risk readiness than Group 2, i.e., those who, on average, also agreed with the requirements for trust building, but to a comparatively lesser extent (Group 1; $M = 3.74$, $SD = 1.27$ and Group 2; $M = 4.3$, $SD = 1.25$). On the other hand, Group 1 had a higher mean score on innovation readiness ($M = 4.04$, $SD = 0.51$) than Group 2 ($M = 3.78$, $SD = 0.57$). We also found significant differences between the two trust groups and their levels of initial trust in the AAL system ($t(141) = 5.37$, $p < 0.001$, $d = 0.93$). Inspection of the descriptive statistics revealed that Group 1 had higher ratings of initial trust ($M = 4.75$, $SD = 0.52$) than Group 2 ($M = 4.23$, $SD = 0.63$). For the categorical factors presence of chronic illness, education and gender, three chi-square tests were run on the two trust groups. No significant differences were found between the trust groups and gender and education. However, we found a significant difference between the presence of chronic illness and the two trust groups ($\chi^2(1) = 5$, $p = 0.03$) with more than half of the

Table 1 Influences of user factors on cluster segmentation in the medical context.

	CLUSTER 1 (N = 89)	CLUSTER 2 (N = 54)	INFERENCE STATISTICS
TRUST REQUIREMENTS	5.39 ± 0.36	4.21 ± 0.51	t(141) = 16.16, $p < 0.001$
RISK READINESS	3.74 ± 1.27	4.3 ± 1.25	t(141) = -2.55, $p = 0.012$
INNOVATION	4.04 ± 0.51	3.78 ± 0.57	t(141) = -2.85, $p = 0.005$
INITIAL TRUST	4.75 ± 0.52	4.23 ± 0.63	t(141) = 5.37, $p < 0.001$
PRESENCE OF CHRONIC ILLNESS	N = 36 / 53	N = 12 / 42	$\chi^2(1) = 5, p = 0.03$

Values represented in means (M) and standard deviations (SD) or frequencies (yes/no).

Table 2 Influences of user factors on cluster segmentation in the mobility context.

	CLUSTER 1 (N = 58)	CLUSTER 2 (N = 18)	CLUSTER 3 (N = 67)	INFERENCE STATISTICS
TRUST REQUIREMENTS	5.54 ± 0.28	3.19 ± 0.52	4.47 ± 0.34	F(2140) = 353.6, $p < 0.001$
RISK READINESS	3.6 ± 1.18*	4.44 ± 1.34*	4.12 ± 1.3	F(2, 140) = 4.2, $p = 0.017$
INITIAL TRUST	4.91 ± 0.47**	4.38 ± 0.7**	4.5 ± 0.64**	F(2, 140) = 9.57, $p < 0.001$
PRESENCE OF CHRONIC ILLNESS	N = 29 / 29	N = 3 / 15	N = 16/51	$\chi^2(2) = 12.15, p = 0.002$

Values represented in means (M) and standard deviations (SD) or frequencies (yes/no). ** $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$ represent significance of post-hoc tests.

respondents reporting a chronic illness in Group 1 and less than a third having a chronic illness in Group 2.

Regarding the clusters identified in the mobility context, five one-way ANOVA's were conducted with the three trust groups as the independent variable and age, dispositional trust, innovation readiness, risk readiness, and initial trust perceptions as respective dependent variables. No significant differences were found for the variables age, dispositional trust, and innovation readiness. However, we found significant differences between the trust groups and their scores on risk readiness ($F(2, 140) = 4.2, p = 0.017$). Post hoc testing using Tukey HSD revealed that Group 1 ($M = 3.6, SD = 1.18$) had significantly lower ratings of risk readiness than Group 2 ($M = 4.44, SD = 1.34; p = 0.038$). Group 3 did not differ significantly from the other two. We also found significant differences between the three trust groups and their levels of initial trust in the SAV system ($F(2, 140) = 9.57, p < 0.001$). Post hoc testing using Tukey HSD revealed that Group 1 ($M = 4.91, SD = 0.47$) had significantly higher ratings of initial trust than Group 2 ($M = 4.38, SD = 0.7; p = 0.003$) and Group 3 ($M = 4.5, SD = 0.64; p < 0.001$). Moreover, for the categorical variables presence of chronic illness, education and gender, three chi-square tests were run on the three trust groups. No significant differences were found between the trust groups and gender and education. However, we found significant differences between the presence of chronic illness and the three trust groups ($\chi^2(2) = 12.15, p = 0.002$) with all of the subjects in Group 1 having a chronic disease, 20% in Group 2, and a little more than 30% in Group 3.

Relationships of Trust and Behavioural Intention to Use Technologies (RQ3). Within the context of video-based AAL technologies, we found significant correlations between the trust requirements and initial trust evaluations ($r = 0.54, p < 0.001$). In other words, with an average high level of agreement with the requirements for building trust, the perceived trust in the AAL system was also on average rather high. Moreover, we found significant negative correlations between individual items of initial trust evaluations and behavioural intention to use video-based AAL systems ("If I did not trust the AAL system, I would not use it", $r = -0.17, p = 0.042$; "Decisions that AAL systems make, would have negative consequences", $r = -0.24, p = 0.003$). A visualisation can be found in Fig. 3.

Within the context of SAV, we found significant correlations between the trust requirements and initial trust evaluations

($r = 0.44, p < 0.001$). Again, this indicates that with an average high level of agreement with the requirements for building trust, perceived trust in SAV is also on average rather high. Moreover, we found significant negative correlations between individual items of initial trust evaluations and behavioural intention to use autonomous shuttle services ("If I did not trust the AAL system, I would not use it", $r = -0.26, p = 0.002$; "Decisions that AAL systems make, would have negative consequences", $r = -0.47, p < 0.001$). A visualisation can be found in Fig. 4.

Discussion

The objectives of the study were to (RQ1) measure trust building requirements in a contextual comparison between a video-based AAL application and a new driving service with SAV, (RQ2) identify distinct clusters, i.e., trust personalities, based on agreement with the requirements, and (RQ3) evaluate the extent to which trust building requirements, initial perceived trust, and willingness to use are related to the described technical applications. Key findings are discussed below according to the research questions.

Trust requirements in contextual comparison (RQ1). In both contexts, there was general agreement on all the requirements for building trust. Perceived technical reliability, as measured by a low error rate, participation in data sharing, and a high level of technology maturity were particularly critical to building trust. In order to find out which trade-offs exist in the context of trust building, conjoint analyses could offer a methodical approach for follow-up studies to examine the relevance of individual requirements in simulated decision-making situations and to identify preferences. We found striking differences in the evaluation of trust requirements between the mobility context and the medical context. Following previous research (Bierman et al. 2020, 2023b; Brell et al. 2019), this suggests that trust does not always emerge in the same way but is a situational phenomenon that needs to be studied contextually. It also means that for each technological innovation, it is necessary to re-assess which factors are particularly relevant and critical to trust in order to promote its development and design in consultation with public opinion.

On a descriptive level, trust requirements were generally more agreed upon in the medical context, except for items related to error rate and data sharing, where agreement was higher in the mobility context. This may be due to the fact that in the SAV

Fig. 3 Relationships between trust in AAL and intention to use (scale indices were used). * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$.

Fig. 4 Relationships between trust in ASS and intention to use (scale indices were used). * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$.

research scenario, the technology was described as fully autonomous, which may have suggested greater technical dependency compared to the AAL technology, where it was described as assistive. Expected consequences of a technical malfunction may be perceived as more serious in the mobility context (danger to life in the case of car accidents). Besides, the availability of data may not be as present or clear to users as in the medical context. We found statistically significant differences in the requirements analysis in terms of data privacy and customisation which were more likely to be agreed upon as prerequisites for building trust in the medical context than in the mobility context. This signals the importance of data access and protection in the context of sensitive medical information whereas data protection about the mobility of people seems to be less of a trust requirement. One explanation could be that the SAV is offered to multiple users at the same time where information is logically shared with more people by using the service. It is also interesting to note that the individualisation of the service in the mobility context seems to play a comparatively minor role in building trust, as individualisation is a unique selling proposition compared to existing mobility offers (e.g., traditional public transport). It is possible that the individualisation of the mobility service is more relevant to the willingness of use, which needs to be measured in follow-up studies. If this hypothesis can be confirmed empirically, the result illustrates the relevance of an initial separate scientific evaluation of the factors influencing trust and acceptance before considering them in context.

Implications of trust groups (RQ2). We have identified different groups of people based on their assessment of trust requirements.

Following Biermann et al. (2022), we thus confirm the existence of different trust personalities in our research scenario. This implies that trust is not only a situational but also an individual phenomenon and that human factors need to be taken into account when assessing trust in automation contexts, as already suggested, for example, in Hoff and Bashir’s (2015) model of trust in automation (see theoretical background for a detailed classification of our results into the state of the art and implications).

All trust clusters differed in their willingness to take risks, the presence of a chronic illness, and initial perceived trust in technology, although the latter was generally high in all groups. The trust clusters in the medical context also differed in their willingness to engage in innovation. Overall, it can be said that people who are less willing to take risks and chronically ill people in particular showed a high level of agreement with the requirements asked about. It is possible that the high level of agreement between these clusters can be explained on the one hand by a perceived need for technical support across contexts due to health circumstances. In contrast, fulfilling the prerequisites for building trust may compensate for uncertainties that may be particularly relevant for these individuals due to their lower risk tolerance. As potential regulators of trust, the identified requirements and conditions must be taken into account in the development and design of technological innovations.

Relationships of trust and behavioural intention to use (RQ3).

In our study, we found correlations between initial trust perceptions, trust requirements, and the behavioural intention to use. We also found initial trust to be higher in the mobility compared to the medical context. While these relationships were stronger in

the mobility context, this signals that trust and agreed-upon requirements of trust play an important role in the intention to use a given technology. It is also important to mention that while the relationships between trust requirements and initial trust evaluations were positive, i.e., the more participants agreed on trust requirements, the more initial trust they had, the association between initial trust and intention to use was negative. Based on the phrasing of the items this means that the less people thought the technology to make bad decisions, the more they intended to use it. Concurring, the less they depended on trusting it, the more they intended to use it. In accordance with this, literature has shown trust to be an important predictor for later acceptance (Pavlou, 2003; Wilkowska et al. 2015; Wilkowska and Ziefle, 2019). However, there are also findings that point to a mediating role rather than a direct effect of trust on acceptance scores (Bodó, 2021; Otten et al. 2023). This could be the case in this study as well and seeing as perceived benefits and barriers are directly related to acceptance, it is necessary to investigate further into how these relationships influence each other and what the precise role of trust is in this regard (Jaschinski and Allouch, 2015; Wilkowska et al. 2021).

Relevance of the findings. This study highlights the importance of individuality and the concurrent need for technology to be adaptive. Both contextual and user-specific influences leading to different evaluations of trust requirements were found in this study. Our study was scenario-based without a real test environment, i.e., we examined the *initial* perceived trust of potential users. Although we did not distinguish between all types of trust, our findings add valuable context-specific information to the general modelling of trust in automation by Hoff and Bashir (2015), prior to interaction, in terms of identified requirements for building trust. These enhance, among other things, the list of perceived risks and benefits (situational trust) and pre-existing knowledge and expectations (initial learned trust) regarding the human-automation interaction (Hoff and Bashir, 2015). Both in terms of trust frameworks such as Hoff and Bashir's (2015) and empirical results such as Biermann et al.'s (2020), we can confirm that disposition and user diversity shape the view of trust, which in this study was obtained by trust-building requirements depending on different clusters. Consistent with previous findings (Bodó, 2021; Ghazizadeh et al. 2012; Lee and See, 2004; Nordhoff et al. 2021), both direct relationships between initial trust and willingness to use new technologies were observed, as well as indirect relationships in the sense that trust building requirements correlate with perceptions of trust, which in turn correlate with behavioural intention to use.

Limitations and future research. This study's greatest strength is the direct comparison of two novel technologies in different automation contexts. Trust transfer and trust universality is a controversial topic without clear boundaries or conclusions (McKnight and Chervany, 2001; McKnight et al. 2011). This research design made it possible to directly compare and identify the trust requirements that are important for each technology, particularly in comparison. This means that in neither context, trust is either relevant or irrelevant but comparing contexts allows for a relative estimation of important factors. However, follow-up studies should expand on this comparison in a both a general comparison of technology and specific use cases. Conjoint analyses could be of help by weighing the importance of factors relative to each other (Offermann-van Heek and Ziefle, 2019; Arning and Ziefle, 2015). Using a repeated-measures approach, we could measure inter- as well as intra-individual perceptions of trust in technologies. However, with any study there are still

weaknesses to be discussed. Firstly, the sample was entirely German-speaking, relatively educated and young. Combined with a comparably low sample size, the generalisability of the results is limited and should be interpreted with caution. Moreover, the description of the technologies varied significantly and might have limited the comparability of the two scenarios. This is mainly because the AAL technology has multiple use cases, depending on the needs and preferences of the user, the type of camera that is used (e.g., infra-red or depth sensors), and the spatial surroundings in which the technology is installed. In these technologies, the use is only decided on once it is clear what care needs have to be met. In the case of a SAV, the technology's purpose is clear much sooner and can be relatively less customised by the booking function. It still limits the possibility of directly comparing the two technologies by the way the scenario was phrased. The medical technology is also assistive, while the mobility technology is autonomous. Moreover, the items regarding the trust requirements were phrased generally, i.e., potentially applicable to any machine or technology. While this has its benefits regarding the generalisability of the results, it limits the individual consideration of requirements because of the lack of specificity. Future investigations might benefit from narrowing down these items into more specific conditions of trust. The results are also correlational in nature and causality cannot be derived. Lastly, we employed a scenario-based design and while this is advantageous in circumstances where a theoretical concept is being studied, the observed evaluations and perception might differ in reality. This gap between reported attitudes and actual use behaviour is also a well-known phenomenon throughout literature (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1980). Similarly to this, evaluations of these constructs might also differ when considering choosing the technology for someone else, such as a relative. As this requires a change in perspective, trust in and acceptance of medical technology might be different if respondents chose the technology for their family members instead of themselves. This poses an interesting question that could be addressed in future studies, completing the picture of the involved parties and mechanisms of technology evaluation. In addition, questions on the trade-offs about the technologies in each context could also be of help. Specifically when evaluating more individual experiences in exchange for more intrusive data collection, understanding when the tipping point of trust to no trust occurs, is highly relevant as technologies could be tailored more towards the end-users. Here, conjoint analyses could again provide meaningful insights into the mechanisms of trust transfer.

Implications for science, policy, and practice. Implications for scientific research, policy and practical development of the technology can be derived from the identified relevant requirements for trust building to manage innovation, but also distrust in technology, as previously proposed (e.g., Bodó, 2021). Data sharing and privacy was a cross-cluster issue (albeit of varying importance) in terms of building trust. Thus, legal frameworks must be created that define which data (e.g., image, biometrics) may be collected and where they may be stored (e.g., on internal or public servers), and that allow users to participate. However, these rules should be made in consensus with public opinion to meet with a high level of acceptance, i.e., scientific studies that record the opinions of those affected on the topic of data sharing, data storage, etc. and integrate them into the design of the legal requirements are necessary. It is also the task of politics to promote this. In addition, technical reliability and maturity were critical for building trust. This has implications for scientific research as a basis for the practical development and production of new technologies. This includes engineering research and

design by integrating the user's trust requirements adapted to the given technological context, but also social science considerations to answer questions such as: Which factors determine perceived reliability (e.g., safety) in each context? Where are the perceived limits from the user's perspective, i.e., what is no longer perceived as reliable and is rejected, e.g., in terms of error rates? Overall, the provision of information on trust-related issues (e.g., data protection, technological maturity) needs to be part of public information and communication strategies that target different audiences. These may be people with different levels of knowledge (including children), for whom the information must be prepared accordingly but also people with different attitudes (technology sceptics vs. enthusiasts), who need to be identified and addressed in an equally appropriate way. The aim should be to educate people about the possibilities and limitations of new technologies, and to avoid unrealistic ideas that could lead to rejection. Moreover, people working with the technology and the users, i.e., the vendors and companies distributing it, can benefit from this knowledge to keep in mind the diversity of potential users.

Data availability

Raw data provided by the participants is anonymized and by default stored in anonymized or aggregated form without the possibility of inferring details of individual persons. Nonetheless, this raw but anonymized data can be made available on request for the sake of further research by the authors.

Received: 21 July 2023; Accepted: 18 December 2023;

Published online: 08 January 2024

Note

¹ "TÜV" (short for *Technischer Überwachungsverein*) is the Technical Inspection Association in Germany and Austria that conducts regulatory tests on technical devices and vehicles.

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Acknowledgements

The authors thank all participants for sharing their opinions on trust in automation. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 861091.

Funding

Open Access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethical approval

Ethical approval was not required for this study which is in accordance with the local legislation in Germany) and institutional requirements. This category spans all non-invasive, non-clinical research on human subjects, where subjects are transparently informed about the purpose, aim, and risks of the studies and when these risks are reasonably low. Participant privacy is a key value that RWTH Aachen University has committed itself to uphold.

Informed consent

The participants were informed that their participation was completely voluntary and could be stopped at any time. The results of the study were intended to be used for scientific purposes and solely to be analysed by the authors. Also, they were informed of their legal rights, data protection regulations that due to the high standard of privacy protection none of their data can be identifiable after collection. All participants were of legal age and consented to take part in the study under these circumstances. This manuscript does not contain any individual details, videos, or images of individual persons. The participants were not reimbursed for taking part in the study.

Additional information

Supplementary information The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-02575-0>.

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